

ASSOCIATION OF ADVERSE OBSTETRIC OUTCOME WITH SUB-CHORIONIC HEMATOMA IN FIRST TRIMESTER

Dr Anum Shabir^{*1}, Dr Kashaf², Dr Samia Malik³

^{*1}PGR, National Hospital & Medical Center, Lahore

²House Officer, Islam Medical & Teaching Hospital, Sialkot

³Head of Department Gynae & OBS at National Hospital & Medical Center, Lahore

^{*1}dr.anumshabir@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr Anum Shabir

Abstract

Objective: To determine the association of adverse obstetric outcome with sub-chorionic hematoma among the patients presenting in first trimester of pregnancy.

Study design: Cohort study

Study place and duration: Department of Obstetrics & Gynecology, National Hospital & Medical Center Lahore from February to August 2025.

Methodology: One hundred and fifty pregnant women in first trimester were enrolled and were divided in two groups depending on presence or absence of sub-chorionic hematoma. All the females were followed-up in OPD until delivery. During follow-up, females were checked for adverse obstetric outcome including fetal demise. All the data was recorded in proforma and was analyzed using SPSS ver.27.0.

Results: The mean age of females in exposed group was 26.95 ± 5.43 years and in unexposed group was 25.99 ± 4.57 years. Out of 150 pregnant females, 20 (13%) females had fetal demise, out of which, 16 (21.3%) were from exposed to sub-chorionic hematoma while 4 (5.3%) were from unexposed group. The risk of fetal demise is 4.8 times high in females with sub-chorionic hematoma (OR; 4.814 (95% CI; 1.526, 15.183, p -value = 0.004). In exposed group, fetal demise occurred at mean gestational age of 18.50 ± 4.40 weeks while in unexposed group, fetal demise occurred at mean gestational age of 19.75 ± 4.03 weeks (p -value >0.05).

Conclusion: We concluded that the risk of fetal demise is four times higher if a pregnant female will have sub-chorionic hematoma.

INTRODUCTION

Threatened abortion is intrauterine hemorrhage without cervical dilatation and tenderness during the first trimester of pregnancy. These bleedings cause maternal anxiety and may be linked to fetal and maternal adverse outcomes. Intrauterine hemorrhages are frequently seen on ultrasound examinations, particularly in patients with clinically-evident bleeding in early pregnancy.^{1,2}

When the chorionic membranes partially separate from the uterine wall, sub-chorionic haematomas appear as hypoechoic, anechoic crescent-shaped regions on ultrasonography.^{3, 4} There is ongoing debate over the clinical importance of sub-chorionic haematomas. Sub-chorionic hematoma-related pregnancy loss is the most often reported adverse result.⁵⁻⁷ A higher chance of unfavourable pregnancy outcomes has

been linked to subchorionic haematoma during pregnancy.⁸ When compared to control pregnant women, the presence of sub-chorionic haematoma is also linked to poor neonatal outcomes, such as a higher chance of low birth weight, low gestational age at birth, low Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes, and NICU hospitalization..^{9,10}

These contradictory findings emphasize the need to investigate whether there is an association of sub-chorionic hematoma with unfavorable obstetric outcomes. Through this study we would be able to find out whether any relationship exist or not. This study might help to comprehend any additional dangers that patients with sub-chorionic hematoma and impending miscarriage are exposed to, and it will provide insight to the healthcare professionals that will enable them to advise these patients for anticipated unfavorable consequences.

METHODOLOGY

This cohort study was conducted at Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, National Hospital & Medical Center Lahore from February to August 2025, after taking approval from institutional review board . By using WHO calculator, sample size of 150 females; 75 in each group was calculated with 80% power of study, 5% significance level and percentage of fetal demise i.e. 15.1% in exposed females and 3.4% in unexposed females.⁸ All females who got filtered by following criteria were enrolled by applying non-probability, consecutive sampling technique.

Inclusion: Females of age 18-35 years, parity from 1-4, presenting for antenatal booking at gestational age 8-12 week (on LMP) were enrolled. Females with sub-chorionic hematoma were enrolled as cases. Sub-chorionic hematoma was defined as presence of crescent-shaped collection of blood (echo-free area) between the chorion and the endometrium, detected on ultrasound during first trimester. Females without sub-chorionic hematoma were considered as controls.

Exclusion: Patients with hypertension, diabetes or renal disorders (creatinine > 1.8 mg/dl or on dialysis), bleeding disorders (PT > 15 sec), multiple pregnancies, absent fetal cardiac activity, history of recurrent miscarriages, history of alcohol consumption, drug abuse, history of usage of anti-neoplastics or anti-epileptics, females undergoing fertility treatment, smoking, infections, uterine distension, previous preterm labour, maternal stress, and decidual haemorrhage were excluded from the study to prevent any bias or confounding effect on results. Pregnant females were enrolled from OPD. Informed consent was taken and demographic and clinical data of females was noted. Females underwent ultrasonography and presence of absence of sub-chorionic hematoma was noted. Females were divided in two groups i.e. exposed and unexposed, as defined in inclusion criteria above. Females were followed-up until delivery. Females were advised to present in labor room in case of active bleeding or severe abdominal pain. In case if female presented with active bleeding and severe abdominal pain, and no fetal movements, ultrasound was done to check fetal heart rate. In absence of fetal heart rate and gestational sac, fetal demise was labeled. All the data was recorded in proforma.

All the data was entered and analyzed using SPSS ver.27.0. Relative risk was calculated to measure association of adverse obstetrical outcome with sub-chorionic hematoma. RR > 1 was kept as significant.

RESULTS

In this trial, total 150 pregnant females were enrolled and divided in two equal groups. The mean age of females in exposed group was 26.95 ± 5.43 years and in unexposed group was 25.99 ± 4.57 years. The mean gestational age at the time of enrolment in exposed group was 10.21 ± 1.45 weeks and in unexposed group was 9.92 ± 1.48 weeks. The mean BMI of females in exposed group was 29.06 ± 5.61 kg/m² and in unexposed group was 28.45 ± 6.13 kg/m². There were 25 (33.3%) primigravida in exposed group while 22 (29.3%) in unexposed group. In exposed group, there were 42 (56.0%) females who were working

women while in unexposed group, there were 37 (49.3%) primigravida. Most of the females had sedentary life style (35 (46.7%) in exposed group and 36 (48.0%) in unexposed group). Table-I Out of 150 pregnant females, 20 (13%) females had fetal demise. Figure-1 Out of 20 pregnant females who had fetal demise, 16 (21.3%) were from exposed to sub-chorionic hematoma while 4 (5.3%) were from unexposed group. The risk of fetal demise is 4.8

times high in females with sub-chorionic hematoma (OR; 4.814 (95% CI; 1.526, 15.183, p-value = 0.004). In exposed group, fetal demise occurred at mean gestational age of 18.50 ± 4.40 weeks while in unexposed group, fetal demise occurred at mean gestational age of 19.75 ± 4.03 weeks. The difference in gestational age when fetal demise occurred was observed to be insignificant (p-value >0.05). Table-II

Table-I: Basic demographics of females recruited in the study (n = 150)

	Exposed	Unexposed
n	75	75
Age, in years	26.95 ± 5.43	25.99 ± 4.57
Gestational age, in weeks	10.21 ± 1.45	9.92 ± 1.48
Height, in meters	1.59 ± 0.05	1.59 ± 0.05
Weight, in kgs	73.45 ± 13.27	71.91 ± 14.25
BMI, in kg/m^2	29.06 ± 5.61	28.45 ± 6.13
Parity		
Primigravida	25 (33.3%)	22 (29.3%)
Primiparous	16 (21.3%)	16 (21.3%)
Multiparous (2-3)	34 (45.3%)	37 (49.3%)
Socioeconomic status		
Low	9 (12.0%)	11 (14.7%)
Middle	10 (13.3%)	17 (22.7%)
High	56 (74.7%)	47 (62.7%)
Occupation		
Housewife	33 (44.0%)	38 (50.7%)
Working women	42 (56.0%)	37 (49.3%)
Life style		
Sedentary	35 (46.7%)	36 (48.0%)
Active / exercise	27 (36.0%)	27 (36.0%)
Normal routine	13 (17.3%)	12 (16.0%)

Figure-1: Fetal demise

Table-II: Comparison of adverse fetal outcomes in both groups (n = 150)

		Group		Odds ratio (95% CI)
		Exposed n = 75	Unexposed n = 75	
Fetal demise	Yes	16 (21.3%)	4 (5.3%)	4.814 (1.526, 15.183) p-value = 0.004
	No	59 (78.7%)	71 (94.7%)	
Fetal demise at gestational age (weeks)		18.50 ± 4.40	19.75 ± 4.03	0.613

DISCUSSION

In our study, we observed fetal demise in 20 (13%) females, out of which, 16 (21.3%) were from exposed to sub-chorionic hematoma while 4 (5.3%) were from unexposed group. The risk of fetal demise is 4.8 times high in females with sub-chorionic hematoma (OR; 4.814 (95% CI; 1.526, 15.183, p-value = 0.004). In exposed group, fetal demise occurred at mean gestational age of 18.50 ± 4.40 weeks while in unexposed group, fetal demise occurred at mean gestational age of 19.75 ± 4.03 weeks (p-value >0.05).

Gunay et al., found that the incidence of sub chorionic hematoma in pregnancy was observed in 33.7% females. A higher number of patients with sub chorionic hematoma ended up in spontaneous miscarriage than females without sub chorionic hematoma (15.1% versus 3.4%, p<0.001).¹¹ In a research by Hanif et al., about half of the 132 pregnant women had sub-chorionic haematomas during the first trimester. Sub-chorionic haematoma was found to be significantly associated with miscarriage, suggesting that the cases group experienced a greater rate of loss (37.9% vs. 19.7%, p-value

<0.05). They came to the conclusion that patients with sub-chorionic haematoma who arrive with a threatening abortion may be at higher risk of miscarriage. The likelihood of an unfavourable pregnancy outcome is increased when sub-chorionic haematoma is present.⁶

While according to Naz et al., the incidence of sub-chorionic hematoma in pregnancy was observed in 30.5% females. A higher number of patients with sub-chorionic hematoma ended up in spontaneous miscarriage than females without sub-chorionic hematoma (13% versus 6.1% (P=0.07)).⁴ Inman et al., also found insignificant association of sub-chorionic hematoma with fetal demise i.e. 19.2% vs. 17.1% (p=0.521).⁷ Additionally, Maso et al. found that the probability of a spontaneous abortion was considerably elevated by intrauterine haematomas detected prior to 9 weeks (odds ratio: 14.79; 95% CI: 1.95-112.09).¹²

The authors of a previous study on the prognosis of very large (> 50% of the gestational sac) first-trimester haematomas observed that very big haematomas were associated with poor outcomes in nearly half of pregnancies, and that the results

were worse when the haematoma was discovered early in the gestational period.¹³ Furthermore, comparable rates of intrauterine mortality reported in pregnant women with and without sub-chorionic haematomas appear to be consistent with the current study's connection of the existence and size of sub-chorionic haematoma with an elevated risk for preterm delivery but not for intrauterine death.¹⁴

Although there was no discernible effect on the outcome measures of ongoing pregnancies, such as gestational week at delivery, birth weight, and delivery route, the presence of sub-chorionic haematoma was also found to raise the risk of miscarriage in patients who experienced vaginal bleeding and threatened abortion during the first 20 weeks of gestation.¹⁵ Furthermore, the authors of a meta-analysis of six studies verified that sub-chorionic haematoma was linked to a higher chance of spontaneous abortion, but not to a significant difference in the rate of premature deliveries or the mode of delivery when compared to the group that was threatened with an abortion.¹⁶

Interestingly, a prior study found that while the study groups' delivery routes were similar, the presence of a haematoma was linked to an earlier gestational week of delivery than the control group. Additionally, pregnant women with sub-chorionic haematoma were at a higher risk of delivering their babies earlier. Larger haematomas were linked to a higher risk of placental abruption and IUGR in addition to an increased risk of premature delivery. Considering that pregnancies with sub-chorionic haematomas are associated with a higher risk of foetal distress due to the increased risk of operative vaginal or caesarean delivery, as well as a higher risk of placental abruption or abnormal placentation, and compared to pregnancies without sub-chorionic haematomas, this seems particularly noteworthy.^{17, 18}

Therefore, compared to control pregnant women, the presence of sub-chorionic haematoma was also linked to negative neonatal outcomes, such as a higher chance of low birth weight, low gestational age at birth, low Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes, and a higher chance of NICU

admission.^{5, 19} Bed rest may be beneficial for the majority of patients with sub-chorionic haematomas, and a follow-up and observational approach is appropriate.²⁰ Progesterone and vaginal lipoic acid have been used to treat sub-chorionic haematoma and signs of an impending miscarriage, however there is currently insufficient clinical data to support these therapeutic approaches.^{21, 22}

In this study, we observed limited number of fetal outcomes (fetal demise), however, we observed that in previous studies more fetal outcomes were studied. In few cases association of sub-chorionic hematoma exist while few reported controversial data. Further studies are warranted to confirm the existence of association of sub-chorionic hematoma with more adverse fetal outcomes.

CONCLUSION

We concluded that the risk of fetal demise is four times higher if a pregnant female will have sub-chorionic hematoma.

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